

SURVEY FLOW:

Block: Default Question Block
Standard: Block 1 (2 Questions)

Branch: New Branch

If

If Q. How experienced do you feel using AI tools in your work? Not at all Is Selected

EndSurvey

Standard: Block 2 (4 Questions)

BlockRandomizer: 4 - Evenly Present Elements

Branch: New Branch

If Q. In the last 3 months, which of the following activities were you most focused on at work?

Development (e.g., coding, bug fixing/debugging, refactoring, maintenance & updates, AI Integration) Is Selected

Standard: Block 3 (10 Questions)

Branch: New Branch

If Q. In the last 3 months, which of the following activities were you most focused on at work?

Quality & Risk Management (e.g., testing/quality assurance, code review, security & compliance) Is Selected

Standard: Block 4 (10 Questions)

Branch: New Branch

If Q. In the last 3 months, which of the following activities were you most focused on at work?

Design & Planning (e.g., system design, requirements engineering, project planning & management) Is Selected

Standard: Block 5 (10 Questions)

Branch: New Branch

If Q. In the last 3 months, which of the following activities were you most focused on at work?

Infrastructure & Operations (e.g., DevOps (CI/CD), environment setup & maintenance, infrastructure monitoring, customer support) Is Selected

Standard: Block 6 (10 Questions)

Branch: New Branch

If Q. In the last 3 months, which of the following activities were you most focused on at work?

SelectedChoicesCount Is Equal to 2

Standard: Block 7 (10 Questions)

Standard: Block 8 (2 Questions)

SURVEY STRUCTURE

Blocks 4, 5, 6, and 7 have the same structure as Block 3.

Understanding Developers' Attitudes Towards Daily Tasks, AI Support, and Preferred AI Interaction Aspects

<<Consent Information>>

Q We're sure you're not a robot, but to prevent a few from sneaking through, would you complete the world's most difficult Turing test below?

<<Captcha>>

Start of Block: Block 1

Experience with AI

We're going to be saying "AI" a lot in this survey. Given this, we should give you our definition of AI. Artificial intelligence (AI) involves systems that can perform tasks and/or create content typically requiring human intelligence, learning patterns from existing data. We're interested in your **direct use of developer tools powered by generative AI models (e.g. ChatGPT, GitHub Copilot, Claude)**, where you engage with these systems to complete tasks, solve problems, or make decisions in various aspects of software development. This could include using AI for writing documentation, collaborating for code generation, data analysis, or automating parts of your workflow, among others.

Q. How experienced do you feel using AI tools in your work?

- Not at all (1)
 - Somewhat experienced (2)
 - Moderately experienced (3)
 - Very experienced (4)
 - Extremely experienced (5)
-

<<Risk Tolerance, Technophilic Motivations>>

Q. Please rate your agreement with the following statements:

	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)	I'm not sure (6)
I explore and learn about AI technologies, even if it's not critical for my job or current task(s).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am usually one of the first to try out new AI tools or features that haven't been proven to work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

End of Block: Block 1

Start of Block: Block 2

Background & Demographics

Q. How many years of experience do you have in the software industry?

- Less than 1 year (1)
 - 1-5 years (2)
 - 6-10 years (3)
 - 11-15 years (4)
 - 16-20 years (5)
 - Over 20 years (6)
-

Q. What gender (if any) do you identify yourself as (check all that apply)?

- Man (1)
 - Woman (2)
 - Non-binary or gender-diverse (3)
 - Prefer to self-describe (4) _____
 - Prefer not to say (5)
-

Q. Where do you currently live?
<<dropdown>>

Q10 **Q. In the last 3 months**, which of the following activities were you most focused on at work? *Please select **at least 2 and at most 3** that apply.*

Development (e.g., coding, bug fixing/debugging, refactoring, maintenance & updates, AI Integration) (1)

Quality & Risk Management (e.g., testing & quality assurance, code review, compliance/security) (2)

Design & Planning (e.g., system design, requirements gathering & analysis, project planning & management) (3)

Infrastructure & Operational Support (e.g., DevOps (CI/CD), environment setup & maintenance, infrastructure monitoring, customer support) (4)

End of Block: Block 2

Start of Block: Block 3

Attitude Towards Development Heavy Activities

For this block of questions, we're interested in **development-heavy activities**, i.e., moments when you're actively writing or extending source code, building new features, fixing bugs, tuning performance, refactoring, maintaining or upgrading modules, integrating AI into products, etc. **Note:** Planning, testing, documentation/collaboration, and deployment are covered in other sections.

Q. Please indicate your agreement with the statement for each of these tasks *in your current work* (mark "I don't do this task" if not applicable):

This task is important for the success of my project

	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)	I don't do this task / N.A. (6)
Coding/Programming (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bug Fixing/Debugging (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Performance Optimization (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Refactoring/Maintenance & Updates (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
AI Integration (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q. Please indicate your agreement with the statement for each of these tasks *in your current work* (mark "I don't do this task" if not applicable):

I personally enjoy doing this task for its own sake

	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)	I don't do this task / N.A. (6)
Coding/Programming (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bug Fixing/Debugging (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Performance Optimization (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Refactoring/Maintenance & Updates (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
AI Integration (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q. How **accountable/responsible** do you feel for the **outcome of each task** in your current work? (mark "I don't do this task" if you don't perform the task)

	Not at all accountable (1)	Slightly accountable (2)	Moderately accountable (3)	Very accountable (4)	Fully accountable (5)	I don't do this task / N.A. (6)
Coding/Programming (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bug Fixing/Debugging (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Performance Optimization (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Refactoring/Maintenan ce & Updates (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
AI Integration (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q. Please indicate your agreement with the statement for each of these tasks *in your current work* (mark "I don't do this task" if not applicable):

This task is demanding, it requires a lot of effort

	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)	I don't do this task / N.A. (6)
Coding/Programming (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bug Fixing/Debugging (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Performance Optimization (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Refactoring, Maintenance & Updates (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
AI Integration (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
This is a validation question. Please mark agree (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

<<Note: Each participant saw a maximum of two attention check questions>>

Q. For each of these tasks in your work, **how much AI support would you prefer to have** in the future?

	No AI support (1)	Low (2)	Moderate (3)	High (4)	Very High (5)	I don't do this task / N.A. (6)
Coding/Programming (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bug Fixing/Debugging (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Performance Optimization (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Refactoring, Maintenance & Updates (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
AI Integration (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q. Where do you want AI to play the **biggest role** for your **development-heavy activities** over the next **1-3 years**? A sentence or two in your own words is plenty.

Q. In the last 3 months, how frequently did you use AI (e.g. ChatGPT, Copilot, Claude) for each of these tasks in your work?

	Never (1)	A few times a month (2)	1-3 days a week (3)	Once a day (4)	A few times a day (5)	I don't do this task / N.A. (6)
Coding/Programming (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bug Fixing/Debugging (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Performance Optimization (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Refactoring, Maintenance & Updates (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
AI Integration (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q. What aspects of your development heavy activities do you not want AI to handle and why? A sentence or two in your own words is plenty.

Q. Please **select any five features** from the list that you think are **most important** for future AI-based tooling support in your **development-heavy activities**. (Click the ⓘ icon next to each feature to view its definition)

- Transparency** (AI explains actions & outputs in-context of use) ⓘ (1)
- Goal Maintenance** (AI sustains alignment with user's evolving goals & use cases) ⓘ (2)
- Fairness** (AI treats all users equally, avoids bias) ⓘ (3)
- Privacy & Security** (AI safeguards personal and team data) ⓘ (4)
- Reliability & Safety** (AI is consistently correct; prevents harmful or wrong actions) ⓘ (5)
- Steerability** (AI lets users control, steer, or override its actions as needed) ⓘ (6)
- AI Accountability** (AI provides clear attribution for its actions and errors) ⓘ (7)
- Inclusiveness** (AI supports diverse users and their needs, including accessibility) ⓘ (8)

<<RAI definitions adapted from prior work, see end of document>>:

Maurice Jakesch, Zana Buçinca, Saleema Amershi, and Alexandra Olteanu. 2022. How different groups prioritize ethical values for responsible AI. In proceedings of the 2022 ACM conference on fairness, accountability, and transparency. 310–323.

Q. Can you share an experience (good or bad) that made **the AI features you selected above** feel important for **development heavy activities**? A sentence or two in your own words is plenty.

Block 4

Blocks with same structure and questions as block 3, updated with tasks belonging to the corresponding categories:

Block 4:

Attitude Towards Quality & Risk Management Heavy Activities

For this block of questions, we're interested in **quality & risk management-heavy activities**, i.e., tasks that help safeguard products before they ship. Examples include writing or running tests, conducting code reviews, and performing security, compliance, or audit checks. **Note:** Development, planning, documentation/collaboration, and deployment are covered in other sections.

<<Tasks in Block 4>>: *Testing & Quality Assurance, Code Review/Pull Requests, Security & Compliance*

Block 5:

Attitude Towards Design & Planning Heavy Activities

For this block of questions, we're interested in **design & planning-heavy activities**, i.e., tasks that determine what to build and how to build it. Examples include system design/architecture, gathering or analyzing requirements, and project management (e.g., estimating effort, planning sprints or releases). **Note:** Development, testing, documentation/collaboration, and deployment are covered in other sections.

<<Tasks in Block 5>>: *System Design, Requirements Engineering, Project Planning & Management*

Block 6:

Attitude Towards Infrastructure & Operations Heavy Activities

For this block of questions, we're interested in **infrastructure & operations-heavy activities**, i.e., tasks that keep systems running smoothly in real environments. Examples include DevOps (CI/CD), environment setup and maintenance, monitoring and alerts, or customer support triage.

Note: Development, testing, documentation/collaboration, and planning are covered in other sections.

<<Tasks in Block 6>>: *System Design, Requirements Engineering, Project Planning & Management*

Block 7:

Attitude Towards Meta Work Heavy Activities

For this block of questions, we're interested in **meta work-heavy activities**, tasks focused on **collaboration, communication, & knowledge building**. These activities often cut across all other types of daily work. Examples include writing or updating documentation, communicating with clients or stakeholders, learning, research & brainstorming, mentoring, and onboarding.

Note: Development, planning, testing, operations, and deployment are covered in other sections.

<<Tasks in Block 7>>: *Documentation, Client/Stakeholder Communication, Mentoring & Onboarding, Learning, Research & Brainstorming*

Start of Block: Block 8

Concluding Thoughts and Sweepstakes Entry

Q26 **Q.** What else would you like to mention about using AI tools in work?

Q27 **Q.** Can we contact you in the future to invite you to participate in follow-up interview studies? If you'd prefer to be contacted, please check the box below:

I want to be contacted for a follow-up interview

End of Block: Block 8

RAI definitions adapted from:

Maurice Jakesch, Zana Buçinca, Saleema Amershi, and Alexandra Olteanu. 2022. How different groups prioritize ethical values for responsible AI. In proceedings of the 2022 ACM conference on fairness, accountability, and transparency. 310–323.

Transparency: A transparent AI system is designed to ensure, as far as possible, that users can see why and how it made a decision or inference in context of the work. These systems surface assumptions, procedures, uncertainties, and rationales right alongside the task, or artifact they influence.

Goal maintenance: A goal-maintaining AI system is designed to stay aligned, as far as possible, with users' evolving objectives throughout a task or project. These systems capture the user's explicit goals/constraints, tracks them across steps, detects drift/conflicts, and proactively asks for clarification or re-plans to stay aligned.

Fairness: A fair AI system is designed to treat all people equally. These systems, as far as possible, achieve equitable performance and experiences across relevant user groups and use contexts; measures, reports, and mitigates harmful disparities and stereotype propagation. A fair system works equally well for everyone regardless of their individual characteristics.

Privacy & Security: An AI system that is designed to have strong privacy & security safeguards for user data. These systems minimize, as far as possible, the collection of sensitive information, encrypt what they store, resist prompt-injection and data exfiltration, and provide clear notice and consent mechanisms.

Reliability & Safety: A reliable & safe AI system is designed to be consistently correct and has strong safety measures. It delivers robust, reproducible behavior with calibrated uncertainty, evaluated on domain-specific benchmarks; prevents and contains harmful actions via guardrails for risky steps. These systems mitigate, as far as possible, physical, emotional, and psychological harms that may be caused due to their actions & outputs.

Steerability: A steerable AI system is designed to respect user autonomy and preserve their agency. These systems, as far as possible, give users multi-step controls to steer (constraints, style, temperature, blocklists), reverse actions (undo/redo, compare-against-baseline), or override the AI's actions easily.

AI Accountability: An accountable AI system is designed to provide clear attribution of responsibility and liability for its impacts. These systems, as far as possible, log decision traces, identify the model or component responsible for each action, and offer channels for appeal, incident investigation, rollback and recourse.

Inclusiveness: An inclusive AI system is designed to support as many users of varied abilities, needs, and working styles. These systems provide, as far as possible, adaptive interactions and workflows, and robust accessibility options to accommodate diverse users and their needs.